

CHEMICAL AND PHYSICAL METHODS OF DISINFECTION IN MODERN ENDODONTIC TREATMENT

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Annotation: Scientific research in the field of clinical endodontics is limited by the complexity and often insufficient effectiveness of the treatment of dental patients with diseases of pulp and apical periodontitis. The study of microbial biofilms and methods of combating them in dentistry, especially endodontics, are not adequately represented in the dental literature. Treatment of caries complications (pulpitis and periodontitis) is one of the most difficult and high-tech challenges of modern dentistry. Primary endodontic treatment often fails, as a result of which retreatment of root canals is an important part of both general and specialized dental practice. A review of available literature sources showed that the level of success of endodontic outcomes in Europe and North America (1990–2002) dropped from 87% to 50%. In Scandinavian countries, the percentage of endodontically treated teeth with endodontic periodontitis is 25–35%. According to S.P. Sulkovskaya (RB, 2004), the prevalence of caries complications in the examined group (3180 adults from various regions of the Republic of Belarus) was $92.55 \pm 1.1\%$, the need for endodontic treatment was 6.19 teeth per person, 2.7 teeth required primary endodontic treatment and 3.5 teeth required repeat treatment. E.V.Borovsky and M.Y.Protasov (RF, 1998) conducted an examination of 528 orthopantomograms (14,784 teeth) of dental patients aged 15-64 years and determined the percentage of unsealed root canals, which reached 81.2%. The percentage of teeth with periodontal complications was 19.89%. A.J.Petrikas et al. (Russia, 2014) conducted a study aimed at assessing the quality of primary

endodontic treatment and the need for repeated interventions. They analyzed orthopantomograms of 900 442 male and 458 female 18-70 years old people without clinical symptoms of endodontic diseases. Of 1,229 teeth requiring endodontic treatment, 349 required primary intervention and 880 required repeat intervention. Scientists believe that the main reason for the failure of endodontic treatment is insufficient effectiveness of exposure to microbial associations that inhabit the spaces of the root canal system of the affected teeth. Unlike primary endodontic infections, which are polymicrobial and characterized by a predominance of gram-negative anaerobes, the microorganisms involved in secondary infections are represented by one or more bacterial species. *Enterococcus faecalis* bacterial strains are more frequently detected in secondary/persistent infections (from 24% to 77%) [8, 20, 30, 33]. *Enterococcus faecalis* is considered a normal commensal member of the intestinal flora and oral cavity. It is a facultatively pathogenic, gram-positive, catalase-negative, enzymatic, non-spore-forming, facultative anaerobe. *Enterococcus* cells are ovoid and approximately 0.5-1 micron in diameter. They occur individually, in pairs or in short chains. Most strains are non-hemolytic and immotile. Enterococci are highly resistant to various environmental factors (high pH, concentrated salts, heavy metals, ethanol, temperature 60 °C for 30 min), disinfectants and antibiotics. Starved *Enterococcus faecalis* cells can maintain viability for long periods of time and acquire resistance to ultraviolet light, sodium hypochlorite, hydrogen peroxide and acids. In addition, *Enterococcus faecalis* can enter viable but unsuitable conditions for cultivation and resuscitate after the return of favorable conditions. The ability of *Enterococcus faecalis* to tolerate or adapt to harsh environmental conditions is an advantage over other types of microorganisms. This could explain its survival rate in root canal infections when nutrients are scarce and funds for root canal treatment are limited [11, 16, 20]. Repeated endodontic treatment should be aimed at preventing the emergence or elimination of enterococci. This is possible if certain treatment

criteria are met: the use of pre-rinsing the patient's mouth with a 0.05-0.2% chlorhexidine solution; separation of the working field by a cofferdam; careful mechanical and chemical treatment of the walls of the root canal; irrigation solutions and drugs for temporary obturation of the root canal are used as chemicals in modern endodontic therapy. The most widely used irrigation solution is sodium hypochlorite (NaOCl). In endodontics worldwide, NaOCl is used in concentrations ranging from 0.5% to 6%. Many studies evaluating the antibacterial effectiveness of various concentrations of Tria hypochlorite solutions claim that the higher the concentration of the solution, the more powerful its antibacterial properties are [11, 15, 21]. However, as the concentration increases, the cytotoxic effect of sodium hypochlorite on living tissue also increases [10, 26]. In addition to the concentration, the amount and time of exposure of the solution are important. NaOCl is rapidly inactivated in the root canal and requires constant renewal [21]. L.S.Buchanan claims that to achieve maximum effectiveness, sodium hypochlorite must be in direct contact with the walls of the root canal for a significant amount of time (20-40 minutes). The optimal time for NaOCl to remain in the root canal is a question that researchers have not yet found an answer to [13]. Another endodontic irrigant is a solution of chlorhexidine bigluconate (CHX). The main property of this solution is its substantivity [12, 18]. The antibacterial effect of CHX also depends on the concentration. In endodontics worldwide, chlorhexidine is used in concentrations from 0.2% to 2%. [13, 27]. According to a survey conducted in 2016, dentists in the Republic of Belarus widely use 0.05% chlorhexidine bigluconate solution [6]. Despite the good antibacterial properties of the above irrigants, it is very difficult to achieve complete sterilization of the infected root canal system [13, 21, 32]. To enhance the disinfecting effect, it is proposed to use intrachannel preparations for temporary obturation. For this purpose, calcium hydroxide (Ca(OH)₂) is most often used, which was introduced into dentistry in 1920 by the German physician Bernhard Hermann [13]. The bactericidal activity

of calcium hydroxide is due to its high alkalinity (pH 12-12.5) and the release of hydroxyl ions (OH⁻) - highly active free radicals in aqueous media. Their effect on bacterial lipids, proteins and DNA damages the cellular apparatus and dramatically alters cellular function [2, 4, 13, 21]. Filling of root canals with pastes containing calcium hydroxide is carried out for a period ranging from one week to six months (there is still no exact data on how long the material needs to be injected). To prepare the paste, finely dispersed calcium hydroxide powder is mixed with sterile saline, sterile water or rinsing solution to obtain a cream-like consistency. The finished mixture is introduced into the channel using a channel filler. Calcium hydroxide extract paste from root canals has certain difficulties. It is believed that up to 40% of the mixture remains on the walls of the channel. This can destroy the adhesion of the sealant to the root canal walls and the tightness of the root seal. To solve this problem, some manufacturers offer gutta-perkapiin with calcium hydroxide, but its effectiveness has not yet been fully studied. Although experiments have confirmed that calcium hydroxide is effective against a large number of bacteria found in endodontic infections, bigluconate 2% chlorhexidine is also used as a temporary internal channel agent like Degel in relation to its effect on *Enterococcus faecalis* strains. In: Telles et al. (2013) claim that CA(OH)₂ achieved significantly better results than dressings with 2% CHX gel, especially in periodontitis peaks. [30] It is also relevant to introduce additional strategies for canal sterilization to increase the success rate of repeated endodontic treatments [13, 17]. Photochemical disinfection (FAD) has been proposed as an effective complementary method for treating internal biofilms. The method was tested in vivo, in vitro and ex vivo and showed high antibacterial efficacy against *Enterococcus faecalis*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Candida albicans* [13, 17, 25, 28, 31]. FAD is based on the photodestruction of pathogenic microorganisms under the combined action of a photosensitive dye and low-intensity light radiation with a wavelength corresponding to the absorption

spectrum of the dye. Upon interaction with light, the photosensitizer changes to a triple state (high energy level) and the released energy is spent on the conversion of molecular oxygen. The resulting product, single oxygen, is able to interact with biological systems and destroy them. Microorganisms destroyed by single oxygen include viruses, bacteria, protozoa and fungi. Effective use of FADs in clinical practice is possible only thanks to the availability of suitable hardware and the necessary dye-photosensitizers. Laser diode-based processing devices in the red (=67020 Nm) and near-infrared (=78020 Nm) ranges and blue strip LEDs (=45020 nm) are the most common. The most studied and used dyes in dentistry are phenothiazines (synthetic non-porphyrin compounds), including methylene blue and toluidine blue in different concentrations. However, these photosensitizers have a significant drawback – tooth discoloration [19, 23, 24]. In search of an alternative to phenothiazines, employees of the Institute of Physics of the Belarusian National Academy of Sciences studied the absorption and fluorescence spectral properties of several preparations based on medicinal plant extracts. Chlorophyll (in the form of alcohol and oil) - a preparation from eucalyptus leaves; Galenophilip alcohol solution) - a preparation from eucalyptus leaves; Diagiperon 70% alcohol and 20% tincture of eucalyptus leaves is a herb of St. John's wort, containing 70% alcohol. It is an agent. Studies have shown that all of the above drugs have certain photosensitizing properties when stimulated in the ultraviolet and visible spectral ranges. But the most promising domestic drug is Diagiperon (Dialec Unitary Science And Manufacturing Enterprise, RB). Diagiperon is recommended as an optimal photosensitizer for photochemical disinfection programs. [5] Its photodynamic effect is caused by both the hypericin and chlorophyll components. For Monday, photosensitivity can be stimulated by light sources with radiation peaks in the range of = 666 and 417 Nm. Currently, laser and LED devices with radiation peaks = 670 and 405 nm are certified in the Republic of Belarus and are used to treat antibacterial photodynamics with Diagiperon. Ozone therapy is a

branch of medicine that includes various methods of using medical ozone for general and local effects on the human body [9]. In dentistry, ozone is used in many forms: water or ozonated solutions, ozonated olive oil and gaseous ozone (ozone-oxygen mixture). Much of the ongoing research into the use of ozone in endodontics focuses on its antibacterial activity. For example, ozonated water (0.5-4mg/l) proved to be very effective in killing gram-negative bacteria such as *Porphyromonas endodontalis* and *Porphyromonas gingivalis*. In a 2007 study on animal teeth, Silveira et al. showed a success rate of up to 77% in the treatment of pulp with ozonated oil as a drug in the canals. Ozone gas in high concentrations is active against *Candida albicans*, *Peptostreptococcus micro* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. In general, ozone is able to kill all known gram-positive and gram-negative bacteria (including antibiotic-resistant bacteria), all known lipid and hydrophilic viruses, all known pathogenic fungi and protozoan spores, as well as plant forms. [13, 14, 17, 22, 29]. The mechanism of the antibacterial effect of ozone is not specific and is associated with the oxidative destruction of proteins and lipids of bacterial membranes. The direct cause of death of microorganisms is, on the one hand, local damage to the biofilm during ozone destruction of the polyunsaturated fatty acids that make up its structure, and, on the other hand, ozone-induced transformation of organelles and enzyme systems due to the action of the weak antioxidant system of bacteria, which is unable to inactivate the increasing amount of peroxide compounds. In addition, human cells have strong antioxidant activity without damage.[9] employees of the Department of orthopedic dentistry conducted several studies aimed at improving the effectiveness of repeated endodontic treatment of permanent teeth in dental patients. Analysis of data from Cone Beam computed tomography (CLT) of dental patients with periodontal and apical diseases. The results of CLT were studied by 30 dental patients (9 men and 21 women 25-65 years old) with different clinical conditions at the stage of diagnosis. In any case, x-ray examination is carried out exclusively on the basis of

the designation of conical beam tomography between PLANEMKA12D, located in the city of Minsk Clinic Dental Clinic. In total, 835 permanent teeth were analyzed in planameca romexis viewer with panoramic, coronary, sagittal and axial species, of which 179 (21.43%) had previously been treated for complex caries. More than half of the previously treated teeth showed repeated signs of intervention (51.39%). Evaluation of sensitivity of Enterococcus faecalis strains isolated from the root canals of dental patients with pulp and periodontitis Peak 2% solution of chlorhexidine bigulconate ("belasol No. 2"/vladimieva, Russia); 3% and 5.2% solution of sodium hypochlorite (3% and 5.2% solution of "belodez"/vladimieva, Russia); polyhexamethylene biguanidine hydrochloride and so on. phenoxyethanol (mukosanin/belaseptica JSC, Republic of Belarus); alcohol-containing sensitivities ("belosanin/belaseptica JSC, Republic of Belarus); alcohol-containing sensitivities ("belosanin/belaseptica JSC, Republic of Belarus); alcohol - containing sensitive substances ("Belosanin/belaseptica jsc, Republic of belarus); alcohol-containing photosensitizers ("Belosanin/belaseptica jsc, Republic of belarus); alcohol-containing photosensitizers ("belosanin/belaseptica jsc, Republic of belarus); alcohol-containing photosensitizers ("belosanin/belaseptica jsc, Republic of belarus); diagiperon"/"dialek", Republic of belarus); 72% calcium anhydrous colloidal hydroxide ("calcevite" / Vladimir, Russia); Gutta par contains 2% chlorhexidine begluconate gel (Tehnodent, rossian); Gutta palm cosanin contains 5% diacetetechlorhexidine (activated chlorhexidine/Roco pen, Switzerland) and 5 2% calcium hydroxide (calcium h ydducise plus/roco pen, Switzerland) in laboratory conditions as gram-positive bacteria. And since it is an antiseptic that has a pronounced bactericidal effect on gram-negative bacteria, flukes and some viruses, it has been involved in the assessment of the sensitivity of the enterococcus faecalis strain to irrigation solutions. The manufacturer recommends a solution for use in alternative dentistry for chlorhexidine bigulconate. "Diagiperon" is a tincture of st. John's wort contains 70% alcohol. In addition to its anxiolytic, antidepressant

and antispasmodic properties, it has antibacterial activity against many microorganisms (Staphylococcus aureus, Escherichia coli, Pseudomonas aeruginosa, Pseudomonas aeruginosa), so it took part in the assessment of the sensitivity of the Enterococcus faecalis strain to irrigation solutions. In some options, the current invention is a method that includes administering the patient with an effective amount of therapeutic compounds (e.g., shigella flexneri1A, shigella flexneri2A, Shigella sonnei, salmonella enteritis, Salmonella typhimurium and Candida albicans), which are resistant to the effects of antibiotics. "Diagnosis" is also involved in further research as a photosensitive. The antibacterial effect of the solution is assessed by the "cup method", and the susceptibility of bacteria to the antiseptic is determined by introducing the antiseptic into the nutrient jelly. The antibacterial effects of highly dispersed calcium hydroxide powder, bigluconate chlorhexidine gel and activated gutta-percha Pen have been evaluated based on modified disco diffusion methods. According to the results of the study, a 5.2% solution of sodium hypochlorite showed higher antibacterial activity than other solutions: all strains of Enterococcus faecalis are sensitive to it in all dilutions.(1, 1/2, 1/4, 1/8). Monday-a 3% solution of naocl. During the growth period (1-10 minutes), the development of all strains of Enterococcus faecalis was inhibited, even with 1/8 dilution. The 2% chlorhexidine solution of bigluconate was found to be effective at the main concentration at any time of exposure. Low CHX levels have no significant effect on enterococci at any time of exposure. Mucosanin and diagnosperone are only effective at the main concentrations of the three exposures we have selected (30c, 60c, 10m). 2% chlorhexidine bigluconate Gel shows high antibacterial properties against Enterococcus faecalis . Significant zones of inhibition of microbial growth (from 5.5 to 14 mm) were observed in all samples. Chlorhexidine pin also shows an antibacterial effect against Enterococcus faecalis. Zones of inhibition of microbial growth were observed in all samples. Calcevit turned out to be minimally effective: the zone of inhibition of Enterococcus faecalis

growth was determined only in some samples and was less than 1.5 mm. Evaluation of the effectiveness of light-activated disinfection and ozonation of root canals in relation to *Enterococcus faecalis* strains isolated from root canals of patients with pulpal and apical periodontal disease. 30 μ l of suspensions from *Enterococcus faecalis*, *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Candida albicans* strains (concentration of microorganisms 1.5×10^8 CFU/ml) were added to single-rooted single-channel permanent teeth (No. 20) prepared in a certain way and sent to a thermostat (37 ° C) for 24 days. After 24 days, the growth of all strains and the effectiveness of the root canal FAD scheme were confirmed by using the PDT laser device (continuous laser radiation in the red spectral range ($\lambda = (660-665)$ nm) as a radiation source (developer and manufacturer - B.I.Stepanov Institute of the National Academy of Sciences of Belarus) and the medical drug "Diagiperon" (Dialek, RB) as a photosensitizer dye, as well as the electric generator "Prozone" W&h, Austria as an ozone source. The device generates 140 ppm ozone at 2 l/min. After 24 days of incubation in a thermostat at 37 ° C, the growth of *Candida albicans* cultures was absent in all samples of the experiment. *Enterococcus faecalis* shows the ability to form a microbial intraluminal community together with *Staphylococcus aureus*. Not only the ability of *Enterococcus faecalis* to survive for 24 days in a sealed root canal, but also the ability of a mixture of *Enterococcus faecalis* and *Staphylococcus aureus* to reproduce is shown. Thus, after 24 days, the total microbial count was on average 4.12×10^4 CFU/ml, which is an order of magnitude higher than the control oM (1.4×10^3 CFU/ml). The studied photoactivated disinfection scheme showed high antibacterial activity against the formed *Enterococcus faecalis* and *Staphylococcus aureus* intraluminal communities. The effect size was 0.65 (0.57–0.72). Gaseous ozone showed lower antibacterial activity compared to the FAD scheme against the formed *Enterococcus faecalis* and *Staphylococcus aureus* microbial communities. The effect size was 0.35 (0.24–0.46).

Conclusion: The carried out study shows the high need of dental patients for

repeated endodontic treatment; Enterococcus proved the effectiveness of irrigation solutions of sodium hypochlorite and chlorhexidine bigluconate used in endodontic treatment in relation to *C. faecalis*; confirmed the expediency of using the proposed light-activated disinfection scheme during repeated endodontic treatment of permanent teeth as an additional step of root canal disinfection.

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